

Brief Report

Life Cycle Assessment of a Novel Lightweight Photovoltaic Module in an Early Design and Research Phase

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Abstract: Worldwide, an increasing number of buildings have photovoltaics integrated in the building envelope, and the demand of lightweight PV has increased. This is due to their potential for deployment in installations where traditional heavy glass-glass PV cannot be installed. We assessed the life cycle of a novel lightweight rigid crystalline silicon cell PV module for a building integrated solution, which is in an early design and development phase. This concept replaces the heavy glass plates of traditional glass-glass PV laminates with a lightweight composite sandwich structure consisting of an aluminium honeycomb core, fibreglass reinforced polymer skins on the back side, and transparent polymer layers on the front side. It is expected to have less environmental impact than the traditional glass-foil and glass-glass PV due to its light weight. While the preliminary results partly support this notion, the design shows promise as it can be further optimised to reduce the impact. Our report addresses this potential by presenting LCA results for the lightweight PV and comparing it to those of reference glass-foil and glass-glass PV laminates.

Keywords: life cycle assessment; building integrated photovoltaic; lightweight; LCA; LCI; BIPV; product development

1. Introduction

1.1. Building Integrated Photovoltaics

Building integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) contribute to the goal of the energy turnaround towards renewable sources by fully utilising building surfaces, such as the roof or façade, to maximise electricity generation. This goal is achieved with typical glass-glass BIPV with a weight of ca. 25 kg per m². A PV laminate is considered as lightweight when its weight is below 6 kg per m². Lightweight PV may be applicable in situations where standard heavy PV cannot be installed. Moreover, it may be easier and more convenient to install and transport. It may also require less material for its production and that of its mounting system, thus reducing costs and environmental impact. Thus, the demand for lightweight PV has risen and various types of lightweight technologies for PV systems in buildings have recently been developed. Typical lightweight PV is flexible, similarly to thin films. However, the lightweight photovoltaic laminate concept in this study is as a building material that needs a robust load bearing capacity (wind, snow, rain) and is resistant towards fire and moisture [1].

The lightweight crystalline silicon cell (c-Si) PV laminates in this study are at an early design and research phase targeting building surfaces where traditional heavy glass-glass PV cannot be installed. The research scope of the technology is mainly on the lamination process. The concept replaces heavy

glass plates with a lightweight composite sandwich structure consisting of an aluminium honeycomb core, fibreglass reinforced polymer skins on the back side, and an ETFE (Ethylene tetrafluoroethylene) foil on the front side. Other processes and materials remain the same as the established c-Si PV laminate technologies (see Figure 1), thus it can minimise initial investment cost and environmental burden by enabling utilisation of existing production processes and facilities.

Figure 1. Layers comprising a glass-glass, glass-foil, and lightweight PV laminate.

C-Si is the mainstream technology in commercial PV markets accounting for 94% of the market share, while thin film accounts for 6% [2]. Despite the emergence of many new technologies, the former is most likely to remain dominant for next decade, driving substantial market growth by ongoing cost reduction and improvement in efficiency [3].

The c-Si cells are wired in series, thus metallic tab wires attached to a front side of a cell are connected to the backside of a neighbouring cell. Interconnected cells are brittle and easily corroded by moisture. To protect against impact and moisture from hail and rain in outdoor environments, the solar cell strings are encapsulated by two sheets of polymer foils (e.g. Ethylene-vinyl acetate, or EVA), which are in turn encapsulated by two sheets of glass. Finally, these layers are laminated under heat and pressure in a vacuum to form a PV laminate. Deployed without a frame, this system is referred to as a photovoltaic laminate, while an additional surrounding frame designates it as a photovoltaic panel. A junction box and two ca. 1m cables are attached to the laminate or the panel for connection to adjacent units.

For a non-BIPV solution, a Tedlar® polymer film is also commonly used instead of a glass back-sheet. However, a BIPV laminate should resist fire hazards and wind loads to comply with architectural regulations on a building façade. Glass sheets are a typical solution to achieve this, as glass is a commonly used façade component under the established building codes. Moreover, even for a non-BIPV solution, glass back-sheets are increasingly popular as they prevent moisture intrusion.

1.2. Life Cycle Assessment

Environmental Life cycle Assessment (LCA) is a methodology to assess all the environmental impacts of a product or a service during the whole life cycle from the raw material extraction to final disposal [4]. Alternative products have different eco-profiles over their lifetime; the environmental impact of one product contributes mainly to its production phase, while that of another dominates

Table 1. Lamination materials for 1 m² of a lightweight photovoltaic laminate. Loss during its manufacturing processes is omitted.

Materials	Width (m)	Height (m)	Thickness (mm)	Weight (kg)	Density (g/Cm ³)
ETFE: Ethylene tetrafluoroethylene	1.0	1.0	0.10	0.17	1.22
EVA, Polymer: Ethylene-vinyl acetate	1.0	1.0	2.15	2.35	0.79
GFRP: Glassfibre reinforced polymer skin	1.0	1.0	1.60	2.33	1.05
Honeycomb core	1.0	1.0	6.00	0.46	0.06

during its use or operating phase. Consequently, LCA is becoming increasingly important in policy and industry.

The International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) standardised an LCA methodological framework and terminology (ISO 14040:2006) [5] and provided general guidelines and requirements (ISO 14044:2006) [6]. According to ISO, the LCA procedure consists of the following steps:

1. **Goal and scope:** Definition of the System boundary & functional unit.
2. **Life Cycle Inventory (LCI):** Elaboration of a mass balance for a process with all inputs and outputs.
3. **Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA):** Assessment of environmental consequences of the LCI such as climate change, natural resource depletion, ozone depletion, ecotoxicity etc. with specific indicators. A sensitivity analysis considers the individual effects of the choices made, i.e. flows and indicators.
4. **Interpretation:** Identification of processes and flows with main environmental impact and recommendation of measures for improvement.

1.3. Purpose of the study

Typically, PV is designed and developed to pass the International Electrotechnical Commission test (IEC 61215) [7]. However, unlike ground mounted PV, building integrated PV (BIPV) systems also need to satisfy building regulations, which are vague or even conflicting [8]. Finally, BIPV should generate electricity with lower environmental impact than that of the existing Swiss low-voltage grid to conform with the national strategy and be widely accepted in the market.

The purpose of this study is therefore to assess the adequacy of the design of the lightweight PV laminate for a building integrated solution via Life Cycle Assessment and support the early stage of BIPV research and development. The methodology is adopted from a previous study conducted by the authors [9] for multicoloured glass-glass laminates.

2. Methodology

The following section specifies the PV laminate and façade installation used in this study. In accordance with the sequence of the four LCA phases in Section 1.2, the goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, and impact indicators used in this study are presented. The impact assessment and interpretations is presented as results in Section 3.

2.1. Specifications

The current physical form of the lightweight PV is a prototype with 16 cells and 0.81 m × 0.81 m ≈ 0.66 m² dimension. However, for the study, it is normalised to 1 m². The lamination materials are presented in Table 1.

2.2. Goal and Scope

To achieve the purpose of the study stated in Section 1.3, the LCA result of the lightweight PV laminate is compared to a reference BIPV system consisting of a multi-crystalline silicon (m-Si) glass-foil

laminate integrated into a 3 kWp façade system, using Ecoinvent [10] data that reflects the market average. The Ecoinvent database contains data of basic materials, energy, waste, and transportation. This data is collected from averages of material and energy flows provided by industrial sectors, expert estimates, and literature values. This study uses the APOS [11] data set, which is one of the three sets of data available in Ecoinvent 3.4.

For a BIPV solution, a glass-glass PV laminate is more frequently used than a glass-foil type. However, Ecoinvent does not contain data of glass-glass laminate. The glass-foil laminate in Ecoinvent was modified to a glass-glass type by replacing only the foil component with a glass sheet and also used as a reference.

The system boundary of the lightweight photovoltaic is assumed to be identical to the system boundary of the reference, differing only in the lamination materials as presented in Figure 2. The final product of the supply chain is electricity generated by BIPV system with the lightweight laminates, and includes all processes for laminate production, production of the Balance of System (BOS), such as the inverter etc. In addition, this includes installation, cleaning and maintenance of the PV installation, and its end of life. The functional unit is a kilowatt hour (kWh) of generated electricity.

2.3. Life Cycle Inventory

As mentioned above, the life cycle inventory (LCI) of the lightweight PV is identical to that of the reference, except for the lamination materials. The quantity of lamination materials can be seen in Figure 3. Other materials, processes, and assumptions for the LCA remain unchanged from the Ecoinvent data.

The total PV laminate weights are 5.5kg, 11.2kg, and 21.2kg for lightweight, glass-foil, and glass-glass, respectively. Consequently, the lightweight PV is the lightest, but also the thickest. The amount of ETFE film and aluminium honeycomb core is 7% more than in Table 1, estimated from similar backsheet foil losses in the reference system data. EVA losses in the reference glass-foil and lightweight laminates are 6%. For the glass-fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) and solar glass, 1% loss was considered.

2.4. Life Cycle Impact Indicators

Impact categories and indicators commonly used in LCA of photovoltaic system are presented in [12, Table 3.2]. For this study, the four indicators in Table 2 were selected, of which GWP was mainly used to present results.

Figure 2. Configuration of the reference in Ecoinvent. A m-Si 3 kWp PV façade generates 55.8 MWh of electricity during its lifetime. The product systems are represented as boxes with grey background containing different lamination materials depending on the PV type, while those with white background are common to all types.

Figure 3. Lamination material breakdown for 1 m² of a PV laminate in terms of weight of input materials (a), and thickness (b) in a final laminate.

Table 2. Indicators selected for the LCIA in this study.

Name	Unit	Remark
Global warming potential (GWP)	Grams CO ₂ -equivalents [g CO ₂ eq]	Contains Intergovernmental Panel of Climate Change (IPCC) climate change factors for a timespan of 100 years [13]
Cumulative energy demand (CED)	MJ-equivalents [MJ eq]	Contains the energy content of renewable and non-renewable primary energy [12]. In this study, only non-renewable primary energy is considered.
Ecological Scarcity 2013	Eco-points [EP]	Eco-points reflect both the actual emission situation and the national or international emission targets pursued by Switzerland [14].
Energy Payback Time (EBPT)	Years	Time required to generated enough electricity, so that Non-renewable CED/kWh becomes the same as one of the reference electricity [12]. Refers to the efficiency of the Swiss low voltage electricity grid at the consumer end (9.43 MJ/kWh acc. to Ecoinvent 3.4)

3. Results

The GWP of each type of PV laminate were itemised in Figure 4. The reference glass-foil laminate exhibits the lowest impact (18.6 kg CO₂ eq), while the lightweight PV shows the highest (50.3 kg CO₂ eq), an increase of 170%. Considering the small quantify of ETFE film used, the resultant GWP is very high, while solar glass exhibits a very low GWP.

Figure 5 shows the GWP per 1kg of material. The GWP of 1kg of ETFE is 129 kg CO₂ eq, a factor of 99 compared to solar glass (1.3 kg CO₂ eq). EcoInvent version 3.3 shows an even higher GWP (318 kg CO₂ eq), suggesting a need for optimisation in the ETFE manufacturing process.

Figure 6 shows the extent to which the GWP of different lamination materials affects the upstream supply chains. In Figure 4, the GWP of the lightweight lamination material is 170% higher than that of the glass-foil laminate. The impact of the materials is reduced, as the GWP of a lightweight PV laminate is only 16% higher than that of a glass-foil laminate. The lightweight BIPV façade installation has a 11% higher GWP than that of the glass-foil façade.

Figure 4. Breakdown of GWP for materials and processes for each type of PV laminate.

Figure 5. GWP of 1 kg of lamination materials. A cell string is not included.

The EcoInvent data considers an annual average yield of 620 kWh/kWp in Switzerland, thus the 30-year lifetime electricity production without degradation for a 3 kWp BIPV façade is 55.8 MWh. The resulting CED per kWh is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 8 shows the fossil and nuclear CED per kWh of electricity generated by the façade. It decreases over time from its initial value of ca. 90 GJ prior to electricity production, which is the total CED of the façade. After a projected 30-year lifespan, this is reduced to about 1.5 MJ/kWh. The EPBT of all three types of PV is 7 years.

4. Discussion

The LCA was carried out under the assumption that all other conditions except the lamination materials remain the same as the reference PV, which is a building integrated PV in a façade. As mentioned in section 1.3, the lightweight PV laminate has been designed to fulfil the requirements of

Figure 6. GWP of a PV laminate (a) and a façade installation (b).

Figure 7. CED (in terms of fossil and nuclear sources) of 1kWh electricity generated from each type of PV façade, and from the Swiss low voltage electricity grid.

IEC 61215 as a PV instead of a building material. Therefore, to assess its acceptance as a BIPV façade component, a façade expert was consulted¹.

A prevalent 60-cell PV module on the current market has 1m × 1.65m dimension. It is typically installed in portrait orientation as described in Figure 9 (a). The façade expert assessed this installation according to the DIN 18008 glass construction standard. There is no established norm for materials such as the lightweight PV laminate. DIN 18008 part 2 states that the allowed maximum sag Cd is 1 cm per 1 m of longitude. The stiffness of the glass-glass PV is about 747 Nm²/m', suggesting the installation of a reinforcement plate with half of the stiffness of the glass-glass PV. Assuming a Young's modulus of 10 GPa (N/mm²) as reference for the lightweight PV, this results in a stiffness of 185 Nm²/m', which was considered too weak.

As a result, an additional mountings are required as indicated by the yellow dashed line in Figure 9 (a). However, mountings at 0.5 m intervals are impractical for façade installation, thus the rigidity of the lightweight PV laminate needs to be increased. The measured Young's modulus for

¹ Personal communication with Markus Schmid, Hochschule Luzern

Figure 8. CED (fossil and nuclear) of 1kWh electricity generated from each type of PV façade and from the Swiss low voltage electricity grid.

the lightweight PV is 17 GPa, so the actual stiffness is $306 \text{ Nm}^2/\text{m}'$. However, a new design of the lightweight PV assumes honeycomb core thickness of 8 mm, resulting in a stiffness similar to that of the glass-glass PV. The stiffness of the current PV is therefore

$$1000 \text{ mm} \frac{(6 \text{ mm})^3}{12} 17 \text{ GPa} = 306 \text{ Nm}^2, \quad (1)$$

while the stiffness of a lightweight PV with a 2 mm thicker core is:

$$1000 \text{ mm} \frac{(8 \text{ mm})^3}{12} 17 \text{ GPa} = 725 \text{ Nm}^2. \quad (2)$$

With the revised design in Equation 2, the GWP of the aluminium core increases by 33% from 9.9 to 13.3 kg CO₂ eq. The GWP of laminate main materials and processes changes by 6% from 51 to 54 kg CO₂ eq, while that of a facade changes by 1% from 7320 to 7398 kg CO₂ eq.

5. Conclusions

To achieve the goal of the Swiss energy strategy, namely to increase contribution of PVs to the national electricity supply by up to 20% by 2050, BIPVs need to be more lightweight to utilise all the available building surface, while generating electricity with a lower environmental impact than that of the existing Swiss low-voltage grid.

The aim of this study was to support the early stage of BIPV research and development by assessing an early design and a product prototype over its entire life cycle, and supporting its market acceptance with minimal design modifications. To this end, the LCA results of the lightweight PV were compared to those of the reference glass-foil and glass-glass PVs.

The most obvious, and perhaps surprising, findings to emerge from the LCA are that the impact of the lightweight PV exceeds that of the reference glass-foil and glass-glass PVs. Moreover, the realisation that increasing the thickness of the lightweight PV by 2 mm results in stiffness similar to that of a glass-glass laminate is important for future developments of the new prototype.

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Figure 9. GWP of a PV laminate (a) and a façade installation (b).

(#153849) and ACTIVE INTERFACES - Holistic strategy for PV adapted solutions embracing the key technological issues (#153762).

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

BIPV: Building integrated photovoltaics

BOS: Balance of system

CED: Cumulative energy demand

c-Si: crystalline silicon cell

EPBT: Energy pay-back time

ETFE: Ethylene tetrafluoroethylene

EVA: Ethylene-vinyl acetate

GFRP: Glass-fibre reinforced polymer GWP: Global warming potential

ISO: International Organization for Standardization

IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel of Climate Change

LCA: Life cycle assessment

LCI: Life cycle inventory

m-Si: Multi crystalline silicon cell

PV: Photovoltaics

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